

PULTRUDED GFRP COMPOSITE REBARS FOR CIVIL CONSTRUCTION: PHYSICAL, THERMAL, AND MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION

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Abstract:

Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) rebars have emerged as an alternative composite material to compete with the durability of reinforced concrete, meeting future demands in applications such as civil construction and urbanization, and featuring weight reduction and resistance to extreme weather without loss of mechanical properties. This study focused on the evaluation of pultruded glass fiber/Epoxy and glass fiber/Polyester REBAR. Three different pultruded profiles were investigated by a set of mechanical tests, physical characterization, and thermal analysis to ensure the quality and reliability of these products. In addition, the properties and characteristics of the composite material were compared with the current metallic materials used in reinforced concrete. The pultruded composites evaluation consisted of constituent content, relative density, moisture absorption, flammability resistance, DMA, TMA, DSC, longitudinal tensile resistance, axial compression resistance, shear stress resistance, concrete pull-off adhesion strength and longitudinal tensile resistance after alkalinity exposure. The results indicated that both the pultruded composites REBAR are in accordance with structural and chemical requirements for reinforced-concrete applications.

Keywords: GFRP rebar; thermomechanical properties; mechanical properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials have been used in several applications including in aerospace, marine, and automobile industries during the past few decades mainly due to their excellent properties such as high specific strength and stiffness, associated with lower density, high fatigue endurance¹, high damping and low thermal coefficient, among others. Recently, the construction industry has begun to recognize the potential of composites for solving the many problems associated with the deterioration of infrastructures².

Concrete has long been used as a building material for its high compressive strength, durability, and low cost. However, its weakness is its fragility and limited mechanical strength, which was solved by using reinforcing bars (rebars), so far made of steel, as a means of increasing its strength. Steel rebar, in fact, is functionally efficient and relatively inexpensive, displays good performance in most cases³.

Despite being widely used in civil construction³, steel rebar has some problems such as high susceptibility to corrosion (oxidation) when exposed to aggressive chemicals, alkaline environment, and humidity. As it corrodes, the steel rebar loses its integrity and increases the tensile load concentration on the concrete, which begins to crack, creating gaps that lead to even greater and faster deterioration of the steel and concrete⁴.

Numerous polymeric coatings have been introduced over the decades to improve sealing and reduce the moisture effects on both concrete, and steel rebar. Hybrid-fiber-reinforced concrete has also been studied to increase the reinforcement concrete durability⁵. Although many technologies have been tested to prevent steel-rebar corrosion, it is not always possible to avoid the corrosion in the long term, making the construction more expensive. The work developed by Harilal *et al.* (2022)⁶ reports a novel ternary cement polymer composite coating (CPFNIC) consisting of fly ash, nanoparticles, and inhibitor with enhanced corrosion protection for steel rebars, at a chloride environment. The results show that the coating significantly delayed the onset of corrosion on rebars in aggressive chloride environments, due to the synergistic contributions from the additives employed, enhancing the corrosion protection⁷.

To create alternative materials for civil construction, a glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) composite rebar was designed for use in challenging and corrosive environments, where weather resistance combined with high mechanical properties are required. According to Jabbar and Farid (2018)⁸, GFRP rebar has a unique combination of mechanical properties that offer a superior alternative to other types of rebar, especially when working in aggressive environments. It has high chemical resistance, high tensile strength, excellent durability and is lighter than steel. The low weight of composite rebar makes it cheaper to transport and logistics, and also faster to install⁹.

The effect of the composite rebar shape in reinforced concrete beam type structures was investigated through finite element analysis by Kadioglu and Pidaparti (2005)¹⁰. The study consisted in evaluating a variety of composite rebar shapes obtained through the pultrusion process, focusing on stiffness and interface stresses. Four different composite rebar shapes were investigated under axial, bending, and torsional loadings, and the results indicated that circular rebar with 6 square ribs with 1° offset offers the best configuration under axial and torsional loadings. As the demand for sustainable infrastructure increases, renewed interest in lifecycle savings and the ongoing costs associated with corrosion have motivated scientists and engineers to search beyond conventional construction materials¹¹.

According to Vemuganti *et al.* (2020)¹², GFRP composite rebars have relatively low shear strength, limiting their use to some specific civil infrastructure applications, such as concrete reinforcing dowels. The authors suggested improving the horizontal shear strength of GFRP rebar by nanomodification of the vinyl ester resin prior to pultrusion, dispersing functionalized multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) into the vinyl ester resin. Longitudinal tension and short beam shear tests were conducted to determine the horizontal shear strength of the nanomodified GFRP rebars. According to this study, the tensile strength of the GFRP rebar improved by 20% and the horizontal shear strength improved by 111% compared to the shear strength of neat GFRP rebars pultruded under the same conditions.

Engineered Cementitious Composite (ECC) is an easily molded mortar-based composite reinforced with short random fibers, and has been applied as an alternative to concrete in tension zones. Wu *et al.* (2022)¹³ developed a new type of composite beam by combining ECC and GFRP rebars. This study investigated the flexural performance of reinforced concrete beams with U-shaped grid-reinforced ECC formwork. The results showed an improvement in the flexural behavior of reinforced concrete beams, with a positive effect on crack resistance at the serviceability limit.

The bond stress distribution and required development length of GFRP rebars were investigated by Makhmalbaf *et al.* (2022)¹⁴. The bond stress distribution in the beams was considered nonlinear; however in the pullout tests, it approached uniformity. The actual development length was found to be 50% to 250% less than that required by the current standards. A new equation was proposed based on the logistic growth function to model the non-uniform bond stress distribution and to estimate the required development length.

The study conducted by El-Sayed *et al.* (2022)¹⁵ evaluated the flexural performance of HSC beams with locally manufactured hybrid-GFRP (HGFRP) rebars with steel wires, through experimental and analytical analyses. The investigation was done to explore the influence of HGFRP bars with varying reinforcement ratios as a new ductile hybrid reinforcement for the beams. Nonlinear analysis was assembled to validate the flexural performance of the beams using the ANSYS program, considering ultimate load, strains, crack patterns, and load deflection curves. The numerical analysis showed good agreement with experimental data regarding ultimate loads and deflections, cracking patterns, and the load-deflection behavior.

Kong *et al.* (2020)¹⁶ investigated the behavior of GFRP built-up hollow and concrete filled built-up beams tested under four-point bending, focusing on shear performance. The experimental results indicated that the GFRP hollow beams failed by web crushing at supports. The longitudinal stiffener has a minor effect on improving the maximum load. Strengthening web-flange junctions using rectangular hollow sections increased the maximum load by 47%. Concrete infill could effectively prevent the web crushing, showing a load increment of 162%. The concrete-filled GFRP composite beam failed due to diagonal stress in the concrete core. The finite element models agreed with the experimental results considering the maximum load and failure mode. The longitudinal web stiffener prevented the web buckling of the GFRP beam, improving the maximum load by 136%.

Although several studies have been carried out to understand the combination of concrete and GFRP¹⁷⁻¹⁹, few have focused on determining the fundamental properties of pultrusion-fabricated rebars. This study identifies the physical, thermal and mechanical properties of epoxy and polyester rebars. The tested GFRP rebars meet the requirements of high-performance structural composite structures.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

The pultruded glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) composites REBAR was manufactured and supplied by TOPFIBER Ind. The pultrusion process was followed by filament winding of a continuous 12k glass fiber rib to enhance adhesion to the concrete, which is considered most suitable for civil construction. The tested REBARs had a diameter of 10mm (d_{rebar}) with 10mm spacing between the rolled ribs. Epoxy and polyester thermoset resins were used for the manufacture of composite Rebars. Both GF/Epoxy (Sample 1) and GF/Polyester (Samples 2 and 3) are classified as medium fluidity F class commercial resins.

2.2 Physical analysis

The determination of reinforcement content (fiber volume fraction) was conducted according to the test method I procedure G in the ASTM D3171 standard. The samples were cut to 10 mm in length and subjected to furnace burning at 800°C until complete degradation of the matrix. The samples were weighed before and after burning. The relative density was determined according to the ASTM D792 standard.

The moisture absorption of the composite rebars was determined in accordance with procedures in the ASTM D5229 standard. Three samples of each material were prepared with 30 mm in length (longitudinal direction) obtaining a 24°C/80% relative humidity (RH) absorption curve in a climatic chamber SOLAB SL-206.

The flammability resistance of the composite rebars was evaluated according to the ASTM D635 standard at horizontal direction, and ASTM E119 standard at transversal direction. In both cases, a

flame burner was fixedly directed at the specimen, and the induction time and occurrence of flame propagation and dripping. Upon ignition of the flame, the burner was turned off, and the lit flame time was recorded. Two samples with 150 mm in length were tested in each direction. Figure 1 shows the apparatus used in the horizontal flammability testing, as an example.

Fig. 1 – Horizontal flammability testing setup.

Reference: authors

2.3 Thermal analysis

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to evaluate the thermal properties of thermosetting resins, including the exothermic nature of the thermal events, in addition to the enthalpies involved in each case, evaluating the curing percentage of the material after processing. The test used to determine these thermal properties was based within the ASTM-D3418 standard. DSC analysis was carried out by a TA Instruments DSC Q-20 2151 equipment with RCS40 refrigeration unit, under N₂ atmosphere with flow rate of 30 ml/min. The tests consisted of submitting 3 mg of each sample in a hermetically sealed aluminum pan in thermal cycles with heating rate $\frac{dT}{dt} = 5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in a temperature range from 25°C to 250°C.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed by an Exstar SII 6000 equipment with 1 Hz frequency, 10 μm amplitude, an oscillating load of 4000 mN, from 25°C to 300°C and heating rate $\frac{dT}{dt} = 10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to evaluate the dynamic mechanical response of the composite rebars as a function of temperature. Three specimens of each composite rebar were tested under oxidative atmosphere by three-point bending mode. Test conditions are in accordance with ASTM D7028 standard by evaluating elastic modulus (or storage modulus, E'), viscous modulus (or loss modulus, E'') and damping coefficient (Tan δ). Glass transition temperature T_g was identified by the peak of Tan δ curve. The 50x10x3 mm samples were analyzed for the DMA tests, as shown in Figure 2, considering the longitudinal direction.

Fig. 2 – Composite rebar machined samples for DMA tests in longitudinal direction.

Reference: authors

Thermal mechanical analysis (TMA) was performed by an SII EXSTAR SS7100C equipment, in three different samples for each composite rebar, in N₂ atmosphere from 25°C to 250°C with a heating rate $\frac{dT}{dt} = 5$ °C/min, and constant load of 100 mN. TMA was conducted according to the ASTM E831 standard to measure the coefficient of linear thermal expansion (CTLE) in both longitudinal and transversal directions. TMA measured the temperature-dependent dimensional changes while allowing the composite rebars specimens to a constant load, thus determining the thermal length change as well as the thermomechanical characteristics of the materials. CTLE is essential for assessing the dimension changes as function of temperature. The mean of CLTE is defined as the slope of a secant through two points of the curve of thermal expansion according to the relation:

$$\overline{CLTE} = \frac{\Delta L_{sp} \times k}{L \times \Delta T}, \quad (1)$$

where k is the deflection (calibration of the length change), L is the calibration length, ΔL_{sp} is the change of specimen length, and ΔT is the temperature difference over which the change in specimen length is measured. The composite rebar samples were machined to obtain the specimens, as shown in Figure 3, for both longitudinal (3 samples/each rebar with 3 mm thickness) and transversal (6 samples/each rebar with 10x10x3 mm) condition.

Fig. 3 – Composite rebar machined samples for TMA tests. (A) longitudinal direction and (B) transversal direction.

2.4 Mechanical properties evaluation

Mechanical tests were performed using the INSTRON 8801 universal testing machine with resources of digital image correlation (DIC), which combines image registration and tracking methods for accurate 2D measurements of changes in images. The longitudinal tensile tests were conducted according to the ASTM D3039 standard and IBRACOM/ABECE annex B, at T=25°C and strain rate 0.01 min⁻¹, limited to 10 min maximum. The rebar samples were cut to 750 mm in length and then inserted into a 19 mm diameter steel metal tube set at 200 mm with medium fluidity epoxy resin for assembly fixture. Figure 4 represents the 6 specimens for each condition used on the tensile tests.

Fig. 4 – Composite rebars inserted into 200 mm in length steel tubes for the tensile testing.

Reference: authors

The axial compression tests were performed according to the ASTM D3410 standard and IBRACOM/ABECE annex C. The rebar samples were cut to 136 mm in length and then inserted into a 19 mm diameter (d) steel metal tube set at 38 mm ($2d$) with medium fluidity epoxy resin for assembly fixture. The free span kept 60mm ($6d_{rebar}$). Figure 5 shows the 6 specimens for each condition used in the compressive testing. To avoid buckling during the axial compression test, a 22 mm diameter steel tube and 136 mm in length was used to cover each sample. After positioning each specimen, the load was applied gradually with a strain rate of 5 mm/min.

Fig. 5 – Composite rebars inserted into 38mm in length steel tubes for the compression testing.

Reference: authors

The compressive strength f_c was determined according to the relation:

$$f_c = \frac{P}{A}, \quad (2)$$

where P is the load in N and A is the transversal section area of the rebar in mm^2 . A metallic mold (SAE 8640 steel) was machined for the shear resistance tests. The tests were conducted according to the ASTM D7617 standard and IBRACOM/ABECE annex D. The rebar ribs were removed from all samples in order to not influence the result of shear resistance. Six specimens for each condition were cut to 225 mm in length for the shear resistance testing. The test was carried out until the complete rupture of the rebars, in the period of 1 to 10 min. Mechanical loading was applied uniformly with strain rate 5 mm/min without impacting the samples. The shear resistance τ was calculated according to the relation:

$$\tau = \frac{P}{2A}, \quad (3)$$

where P is the rupture load and A is the transversal section area of the rebars without ribs.

Fig. 6 – Metallic mold machined and used on the shear resistance testing.

Reference: authors

The adhesion tests were based on the determination of the values of adhesion stress in a pullout test of the rebar embedded in a concrete cube. The tests are in accordance with the ASTM D7913 standard and IBRACOM/ABECE annex E procedures. The concrete was prepared according to ABNT NBR 5738 standard using unit trace of 2 (concrete):3.5 (gravel):3.5 (sand)+ 0.840 (water) = 2.7. A concrete mixer was used to homogenize the mixture for 10 min, which was then poured into wooden boxes covered with polyamide 6 (PA6) plates to ensure a good surface finish of the block (concrete cube). The concrete adhesion test samples remained for 28 days for total cure of the concrete. The wooden boxes (cube) have 200 mm of edge, and the samples have 750 mm in length inserted into 200 mm steel tube (19 mm diameter). A 22 mm diameter steel tube was also used to create the non-adhered gap. Figure 7 shows the apparatus used on the adhesion testing.

Fig. 7 – Concrete adhesion testing setup. (A) Schematic of the sampling preparation, (B) sample being tested, (C)

PA6 square boxes, (D) wooden boxes and (E) concrete adhesion test sampling.

Reference: authors

The concrete adhesion stress at axial direction τ_r is calculated according to equation 4:

$$\tau_r = \frac{P}{cL_{fb}}, \quad (4)$$

where P is the applied load, c is the rebar perimeter (πd_{rebar}) and L_{fb} length of rebar insertion in the concrete.

To determine the tensile strength after exposure to alkalinity, the rebar samples were left for 30 days' immersion in a solution of 118.5 g CaOH (calcium hydroxide); 0.9 g of NaOH (sodium hydroxide); 24.2 g of KOH (potassium hydroxide); for every 1L of deionized water. A mixing machine was used for 3 min for heterogenization, and then poured the solution into a closed container with the samples inside of it. The tensile test after alkaline exposure was conducted according to the ASTM D3039 standard and IBRACON/ABECE annex G, at the same conditions mentioned before. Figure 8 shows the alkaline solution preparation.

Fig. 8 – Alkaline solution preparation and being poured into a container. (A) Weighing the alkaline components, (B) alkaline solution after mixed and (C) rebar samples immersed in the alkaline solution.

Reference: authors

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Physical properties

Table 1 presents the results of the relative density of the composite rebars.

Tab. 1 – Summary of relative density determination of the composite rebars.

Sample	m_i (g)	m_f (g)	$\delta \text{ water}^{25^\circ\text{C}}$ (g/cm ³)	$D^{25^\circ\text{C}}$ (g/cm ³)	Mean (g/cm ³)	Standard Deviation (g/cm ³)
1	1	2.5647	1.1936	1.8649	1.8547	0.0104
	2	2.6764	1.2380	0.9970		
	3	2.6661	1.2247	1.8441		
2	1	2.5920	1.1741	1.8225	1.8199	0.0035
	2	2.6482	1.1943	0.9970		
	3	2.6132	1.1828	1.8214		
3	1	2.4894	1.1096	1.7988	1.7772	0.0214
	2	2.4034	1.0547	0.9970		
	3	2.4758	1.0702	1.7561		

* m_i = initial mass; m_f = final mass after burning; $\delta \text{ water}^{25^\circ\text{C}}$ = water density at 25°C; $D^{25^\circ\text{C}}$ = composite rebar relative density at 25°C.

Reference: authors

The rebars have 4.17% difference when comparing between relative densities, which is in

accordance with GF/epoxy and GF/polyester structural composites. The fiber volume fraction determination is summarized in Table 2.

Tab. 2 – Summary of reinforcement volume determination of the composite rebars.

Sample	m_c (g)	m_{GF} (g)	D^{25C} (g/cm ³)	D_{GF} (g/cm ³)	Fiber Volume (%)	Mean of Fiber Volume (%)
1	2.6150	1.7862	1.8547		49.88	49.70
	2.7147	1.8510			49.79	
	2.6700	1.7986			49.19	
	2.6418	1.8057			49.91	
	2.7320	1.8654			49.86	
	2.7554	1.8718			49.60	
2	2.6573	1.9531	1.8199	2.54	52.66	52.38
	2.7100	1.9469			51.48	
	2.6137	1.9037			52.19	
	2.6126	1.9180			52.60	
	2.6912	1.9841			52.83	
	2.6046	1.9100			52.54	
3	2.5346	1.9461	1.7772		53.72	53.28
	2.4384	1.8624			53.44	
	2.4755	1.8705			52.87	
	2.5792	1.9633			53.26	
	2.5328	1.9191			53.01	
	2.4823	1.8942			53.39	

* m_c = composite rebar mass; m_{GF} = glass fiber mass; D_{GF} = glass fiber density.

Reference: authors

The rebars presented fiber volume fraction compatible with structural composites close to 50% of reinforcement²⁰⁻²². Structural composite materials must meet critical engineering conditions of variable stress state, fluctuating temperature and harsh environment, where the goal is to design large composite structures for longevity, durability and reliability²³.

Fig. 9 – 24°C/80% RH absorption curve for samples 1, 2 and 3 until saturation.

Reference: authors

Sample 1 (GF/Epoxy) presented moisture absorption saturation for 4 days. Differently, samples 2 and 3 (GF/Polyester) presented two phases of RH absorption. During the first 2 days of test, the RH absorption was more intense, and then it was progressively decreasing until saturation in 6 days of the test. The composite rebars have mean of 0.63%, 2.07% and 2.10% of RH absorption, respectively. These values meet the RH absorption values of structural composite materials, approximately 2%. According to Dhakal *et al.* (2016)²⁴, moisture absorption of composite materials may be characterized through comparable sorptivity values, i.e., the material's ability to absorb and transmit water through it via capillary suction, which may be obtained by Fick's law. Diffusion is the principal mechanism for moisture ingress and although it may occur due to voids within the matrix phase leading to effects such as blistering for gel coats, it is predominantly related to interfacial ingress between fibers and matrix. Water diffusion into polymer composites involves further displacement of fluid molecules from a region of high concentration to lower concentration. Due to the moisture absorption revealed in the results shown Figure 9, the GFRP rebars present a fickian behavior.

The results of the flammability tests are intended to serve as a preliminary indication of their

acceptability with respect to fire resistance, fire spread, and drip. The final acceptance of the material is conditioned to its use in civil construction and in accordance with the applicable standard. The results of the flammability tests are listed in Table 3.

Tab. 3 – Results of flammability test showing the induction, test end and flame lit times.

Sample	Standard	Induction time (min)	Test end time (min)	Flame lit time (min)	Drip
1	ASTM D635	1:08	4:16	0:00	No
2		0:38	3:11	0:00	No
3		0:36	2:25	0:30	No
1	ASTM D3801	1:09	2:03	intermittent	No
2		0:46	2:00	intermittent	No
3		0:41	2:03	intermittent	No

Reference: authors

Fig. 10 – Flammability behavior of the composite rebars in the horizontal direction. (A) sample 1, (B) sample 2 and (C) sample 3.

Reference: authors

Fig. 11 – Flammability behavior of the composite rebars in the vertical direction. (A) sample 1, (B) sample 2 and (C) sample 3.

Reference: authors

The ASTM D635 standard evaluates the flammability of the rebar in the horizontal position, and its results are used for material validation. None of the samples showed dripping and flame propagation. Sample 1 has a longer induction time than samples 2 and 3. The longer the induction time, the greater the resistance of the material to contain the flame, that is, the greater the heat energy required for the material to ignite. However, when the samples were tested in the vertical direction (ASTM D3801 standard), all of them showed intermittent flame propagation. This result means that the firing of REBAR, under favorable conditions of high oxygenation and high amount of resin, can be continuously and intermittently until all the resin is burned.

As REBAR is an internal component in the concrete structure, the flow of oxygen in contact with the composite is practically null, which significantly reduces the flammability of the material. The rebars, therefore, showed high flammability resistance.

3.2 Thermal properties

The results of DSC experiments are summarized in Table 4, showing the values obtained for T_g and curing conditions.

Tab. 4 – Results of flammability test showing the induction, test end and flame lit times.

Sample	T _g (°C)	Mean of T _g (°C)	T _{cure} (°C)	Mean of T _{cure} (°C)	Cure condition
1.1	127.6		-		Total
1	1.2	126.3	-	-	Total
	1.3		-		Total
2.1	124.1		180.9		Partial (>0.95%)
2	2.2	123.6	177.7	179.3	Partial (>0.95%)
	2.3		-		Total
3.1	122.5		181.1		Partial (>0.95%)
3	3.2	125.7	182.8	181.9	Partial (>0.95%)
	3.3		181.9		Partial (>0.95%)

* T_g = Glass transition temperature; T_{cure} = Exothermic peak temperature.

Reference: authors

Sample 1 has mean of T_g = 126.3 °C and is fully cured. Sample 2 has mean of T_g = 123.6 °C and mean of T_{cure} = 179.3 °C. The presence of the exothermic peak (heating 1) indicates that the curing process was partial, since there is heat release associated with the thermal phenomenon of curing of the thermoset resin. The same peak was not observed during heating 2, as heating 1 was able to fully cure the sample. Sample 2.3 did not show an exothermic peak during heating 1. Therefore, sample 2 has heterogeneity in the resin curing process, most likely due to (1) insufficient amount of catalyst, (2) insufficient mixing and/or (3) insufficient cure. However, the cure enthalpy did not exceed 5% when comparing with a fully cured material enthalpy. This level is acceptable for practical enforcement. Similar to sample 2, sample 3 has mean of T_g = 125.7 °C and mean of T_{cure} = 181.9 °C. The curing process was partial, indicated by the presence of an exothermic peak in heating 1.

Fig. 12 – Heat flow versus temperature DSC curves of the composites rebars.

Reference: authors

DMA was used to determine T_g of the composite rebars, according to the $\text{Tan } \delta$ method. At the T_g , the storage modulus (E') decreases dramatically and the loss modulus (E'') reaches a maximum value. Temperature-sweeping DMA is often used to characterize T_g of thermoset materials. The temperature limit for applicability of repairs is defined by $T_{\text{onset}E'}$ in order to guarantee that the mechanical properties of the materials remain stable. Table 5 presents the results of DMA.

Tab. 5 – DMA results showing T_g and $T_{\text{onset}E'}$ of the composite rebars.

Sample	$T_{\text{onset}E'}$ (°C)	$\text{Tan } \delta T_g$ (°C)	Mean of $T_{\text{onset}E'}$ (°C)	Mean of $\text{Tan } \delta T_g$ (°C)
1.1	123	144		
1.2	121	143	122	143
1.3	121	143		
2.1	102	143		
2.2	89	144	94	143
2.3	91	143		
3.1	89	144		
3.2	93	158	90	151
3.3	88	150		

Reference: authors

Figures 13 to 15 show the DMA curves for the rebar samples. They show how the modulus E' and E'' values change as a function of temperature. The T_g can be seen as a peak in the $\text{Tan } \delta$ curve. Temperatures above $T_{\text{onset}E'}$ imply a progressive loss of the material's mechanical properties, thus defining the operational temperature limit of the rebars.

Fig. 13 – Typical DMA curve for the sample 1.

Reference: authors

Fig. 14 – Typical DMA curve for the sample 2.

Reference: authors

Fig. 15 – Typical DMA curve for the sample 3.

Reference: authors

TMA tests determined the CLTE of rebars in both the longitudinal and transverse directions. The results were important to evaluate the compatibility of composite rebars when combined with concrete regarding expansion/contraction as a function of temperature. Temperature-dependent dimensional changes determine the suitability of composite rebar applications. The TMA results are listed in Table 6.

Table 6 – CLTE determination in longitudinal and transversal direction obtained by TMA.

Sample	Transversal		Longitudinal	
	CLTE _L (µm/m°C)	Mean of CLTE _L (µm/m°C)	CLTE _T (µm/m°C)	Mean of CLTE _T (µm/m°C)
1	1.1	0.14	0.022	0.018
	1.2	0.14	0.020	
	1.3	0.14	0.013	
	1.4	0.15	-	
	1.5	0.16	-	
	1.6	0.18	-	
2	2.1	0.21	0.016	0.017
	2.2	0.20	0.015	
	2.3	0.22	0.019	
	2.4	-	-	
	2.5	0.16	-	
	2.6	0.17	-	
3	3.1	0.19	0.020	0.018

3.2	0.17	0.017
3.3	0.16	0.018
3.4	0.16	-
3.5	-	-
3.6	0.14	-

* $CLTE_L$ = Coefficient of Linear Thermal Expansion in longitudinal direction; $CTLE_T$ = Coefficient of Linear Thermal Expansion in transversal direction.

Reference: authors

Bonding between GFRP bars and concrete depends on several parameters comprising environmental agents as the service temperature. Typically, GFRP rebars present high values of the transverse coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) with respect to concrete; as a consequence, when the temperature increases, tensile stresses take place within the concrete that may produce splitting cracks affecting the bonding performance²⁵.

Fig. 16 – Typical TMA curve for sample 1 to determine $CTLE_T$ from 25°C to 75°C.

Reference: authors

Fig. 17 – Typical TMA curve for sample 2 to determine $CTLE_T$ from 25°C to 75°C.

Reference: authors

Fig. 18 – Typical TMA curve for sample 3 to determine CTLE_T from 25°C to 75°C.

Reference: authors

Fig. 19 – Typical TMA curve for sample 1 to determine $CTLE_L$ from 25°C to 75°C.

Reference: authors

Fig. 20 – Typical TMA curve for sample 2 to determine $CTLE_L$ from 25°C to 75°C.

Reference: authors

Fig. 21 – Typical TMA curve for sample 3 to determine $CTLE_L$ from 25°C to 75°C.

Reference: authors

The values obtained of CLTE in longitudinal and transversal directions are compatible with structural composites, and lower than other material as concrete and steel usually used on civil construction. TMA revealed that composite rebars have high dimensional stability.

Mechanical properties

Tensile tests were applied to composite rebar before and after alkalinity exposure. Table 7 summarizes the mechanical properties of the composite rebars.

Table 7 – Tensile test results before and after alkalinity exposure.

Sample	Before alkalinity exposure		After Alkality exposure		Difference in mean (%)	
	σ (MPa)	E (GPa)	σ (MPa)	E (GPa)	σ (MPa)	E (GPa)
1	993.08	64.91	933.75	34.36		
2	1004.39	64.31	928.38	45.06		
3	1060.61	41.57	957.26	40.24		
4	867.04	46.50	878.67	47.51		
5	831.35	46.22	938.65	43.19		
6	983.42	42.38	882.76	47.54		
<i>Mean</i>	956.65	50.98	919.91	42.98	-3.84	-15.68
<i>Standard Deviation</i>	88.16	10.74	31.90	5.04		

2	1	1015.00	47.27	1066.39	54.17		
	2	1025.39	41.97	1032.67	38.07		
	3	1064.91	44.04	976.86	40.53		
	4	1005.41	56.55	1004.70	45.62		
	5	1037.90	42.41	947.53	58.72		
	6	971.82	47.46	1010.32	41.54		
<i>Mean</i>		1020.07	46.62	1006.41	46.44	-1.33	-0.38
<i>Standard Deviation</i>		31.39	5.40	41.58	8.24		
3	1	1010.78	59.02	814.11	38.03		
	2	942.75	43.57	949.41	54.47		
	3	1039.64	39.48	934.62	41.27		
	4	998.74	48.79	833.46	50.72		
	5	928.65	42.47	974.25	52.10		
	6	1019.60	51.91	988.96	39.59		
<i>Mean</i>		990.03	47.54	915.80	46.03	-7.49	-3.17
<i>Standard Deviation</i>		44.37	7.20	73.99	7.18		

* σ = tensile strength; E = Modulus of Elasticity.

Reference: authors

Sample 1 presented decrease of 15.68% in E after alkalinity exposure, higher than samples 2 and 3 where are observed 0.38% and 3.17% of decrease, respectively. Thus, epoxy resin is more susceptible to the negative effects of alkalinity exposure than polyester. The composite rebars have high tensile strength, compatible with structural composite. However, the intrinsic characteristic of high elastic deformation of composite materials is responsible for the reduction of E when compared to metallic materials usually used in reinforced concrete.

Fig. 22 – Typical stress *versus* strain curve for composite rebars.

Reference: authors

Figure 23 presents the failure modes of the composite rebars after the tensile test. The failure modes showed that the fibers suffered rupture, but rupture of the rebars in their entirety was not observed, not even in the tensile test after exposure to alkaline environment.

Fig. 23 – Failure modes of composites rebars after the tensile tests, sequentially samples 1, 2 and 3.

Reference: authors

The compressive tests results are listed in Table 8.

Table 8 – Compressive test results of the composite rebars.

Sample	P (N)	f_c (MPa)	
1.1	65598.09	835.22	
1.2	50475.06	642.66	
1.3	55335.81	704.55	
1	1.4	32541.00	414.32
	1.5	32769.23	417.23
	1.6	44982.59	572.73
	1.7	56688.70	721.78
<i>Mean</i>	48341.50	615.50	
<i>Standard Deviation</i>	12412.16	158.03	

2	2.1	54272.06	691.01
	2.2	51474.99	655.39
	2.3	35182.58	447.95
	2.4	34271.28	436.35
	2.5	36534.31	465.16
	2.6	40652.14	517.59
<i>Mean</i>		42064.56	535.58
<i>Standard Deviation</i>		8697.75	110.74
3	3.1	25791.78	328.39
	3.2	28852.39	367.36
	3.3	20286.48	258.29
	3.4	21216.28	270.13
	3.5	25832.52	328.90
	3.6	30483.33	388.12
<i>Mean</i>		25410.46	323.53
<i>Standard Deviation</i>		4043.53	51.48

Reference: authors

The sample 3 presented lower value of compressive strength, comparable with sample 1 and 2. Figure 24 shows a representative curve of compressive stress (σ_c) versus compressive strain (ϵ_c) of the composite rebars.

Fig. 24 – Typical compressive stress versus strain curves for the composite rebars.

Reference: authors

Figure 25 presents the failure modes of composite rebars after the compressive tests.

Fig. 25 – Failure modes of composites rebars after the compressive tests, sequentially samples 1, 2 and 3.

Reference: authors

Table 9 shows the results of the shear resistance tests of composite rebars.

Table 9 – Shear resistance test results of the composite rebars.

Sample	P (N)	τ (MPa)	
1	1.1	35568.62	226.44
	1.2	35527.23	226.18
	1.3	32922.31	209.60
	1.4	34007.04	216.50
	1.5	33861.54	215.58
	1.6	37043.55	235.83
<i>Mean</i>	34821.72	221.69	
<i>Standard Deviation</i>	1495.70	9.52	
2	2.1	25168.08	160.23
	2.2	18220.54	116.00
	2.3	24894.61	158.49
	2.4	23296.56	148.31
	2.5	24971.01	158.98
	2.6	24069.05	153.23
<i>Mean</i>	23436.64	149.21	
<i>Standard Deviation</i>	2649.72	16.87	
3	3.1	24306.87	154.75
	3.2	29504.17	187.83
	3.3	30143.45	191.90
	3.4	27783.72	176.88
	3.5	21082.86	134.22

	3.6	34203.78	217.75
<i>Mean</i>	27837.48	177.22	
<i>Standard Deviation</i>	4619.92	29.41	

Reference: authors

Fig. 26 – Typical shear resistance load versus displacement curves for the composite rebars.

Reference: authors

Sample 1 presented the higher values of shear resistance, when compared with samples 2 and 3. Figure 26 is a representative curve of load versus displacement for the composite rebars. Figure 27 presents the results of failure modes of composite rebars after the shear resistance tests. All specimens were ruptured in the rebar cross section.

Fig. 27 – Failure modes of composites rebars after the shear tests, sequentially samples 1, 2 and 3.

Reference: authors

Table 10 – Concrete/rebars pull-off adhesion strength test results.

Sample	τ (MPa)	Displacement (mm)	τ_r (MPa)	
1	1.1	135.09	3.69	6.87
	1.2	155.17	3.29	7.89
	1.3	186.83	3.42	9.51
	1.4	174.49	4.01	8.88
	1.5	171.54	4.19	8.73
	1.6	155.80	3.97	7.93
	Mean	163.15	3.76	8.30
Standard Deviation	18.25	0.36	0.93	
2	2.1	274.73	7.85	13.98
	2.2	251.74	10.57	12.81
	2.3	282.14	10.70	14.36
	2.4	243.63	7.70	12.40
	2.5	243.79	7.50	12.41
	2.6	211.67	6.78	10.77
	Mean	251.28	8.52	12.79
Standard Deviation	25.24	1.68	1.28	
3	3.1	177.01	6.95	9.01
	3.2	279.70	10.91	14.23
	3.3	299.47	7.31	15.24
	3.4	271.47	9.51	13.82
	3.5	271.50	6.88	13.82
	3.6	263.31	4.47	13.40
	Mean	260.41	7.67	13.25
Standard Deviation	42.68	2.25	2.17	

Reference: authors

Table 10 shows the results of the shear resistance tests of composite rebars. Although the samples 2 and 3 presented adhesion stress τ_r higher than sample 1, the composite rebars tested have

compatible τ_r when compared to metallic rebars ($\tau_r \sim 10 \text{ MPa}$)²⁶. Figure 28 shows a representative curve of tension *versus* displacement used to obtain τ_r of composite rebars.

Fig. 28 – Typical tension *versus* displacement curve used to calculate the adhesion tension of concrete/rebars.

Reference: authors

(1)

4. CONCLUSION

The evaluation of the physical, thermal and mechanical properties carried out in the rebars revealed that the material shows compatibility and competitiveness for applications in civil construction. A major advantage of composite rebars is their significantly reduced weight, lowering the transportation and logistics costs. According to thermal analysis, the pultruded composites have properties compatible with high-performance structural materials. The high chemical and dimensional stability of the rebar surpass the metallic rebars usually used in reinforced concrete. Although composite rebar has a lower modulus of elasticity than, for example, steel, the tensile strength is approximately four times higher. The adhesion to concrete also presented values compatible with steel rebars used as reinforcement in concrete. The presence of ribs that surround the rebar is responsible to enhance the adhesion. The ease of production in conjunction with options for different thermoset resins expands the range of products and applicability of these materials. Composite rebars represent a promising advancement in civil construction. Although the overall properties are similar, GF/Epoxy rebars exhibited superior performance as compared to GF/Polyester. Effective curing also suggests a more refined manufacturing process.

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